

ANISOTROPIC VISCOSITIES OF AN ORIENTED FIBER ASSEMBLY WITH
TEMPERATURE AND STRAIN RATE DEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

By incorporating the Carreau model to describe the matrix viscosity, previously developed relations for the effective viscosities of a collimated discontinuous fiber filled fluid are extended to include zero-shear viscosity and temperature dependence. These new relations, in conjunction with experimental data for PEEK, are employed to determine effective properties of the anisotropic fiber assembly. A decrease in the maximum Newtonian strain rate of the fiber assembly as compared to the neat PEEK is shown. The influence of the Carreau model parameters on the effective longitudinal elongational viscosity is illustrated.

KEYWORDS: Micromechanics, Anisotropic, Nonlinear, Long Fiber Composite, Flow Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

In several earlier papers (1-3) the authors developed models which predict the primary viscosities of an anisotropic incompressible material consisting of collimated, long discontinuous fibers suspended in a fluid matrix. A state of transverse isotropic symmetry is assumed. These models were developed by assuming the kinematics of adjacent rigid fibers and determining the resulting shear stress in the fluid due to applied fiber velocity fields. This procedure allows for the prediction of the effective properties which include longitudinal elongational, in-plane shearing, transverse elongational and transverse shearing viscosities. Explicit expressions have been developed for each of the effective viscosities for both a

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Newtonian and a power law matrix fluid. Table 1 shows a summary of these results in terms of fiber volume fraction, f , fiber aspect ratio, L/D , and matrix viscosity, η .

A deficiency of the power law constitutive relation for a shear thinning fluid is its lack of a finite zero-shear viscosity. In the present work, an expression for a matrix viscosity which exhibits a zero-shear viscosity and includes a temperature dependence is introduced into the relations for the effective material properties.

2. DEVELOPMENT

The effective viscosities shown in Table 1 fail to capture all the characteristics exhibited by polymer melts such as dependence on shear rate and temperature. Carreau (4,5) has introduced the following empirical rheological model to describe the non-Newtonian behavior of such a fluid.

$$\eta = \bar{\eta}_0 \left[1 + (\bar{\lambda} \dot{\gamma})^2 \right]^{(n-1)/2} \quad (1)$$

The onset of the nonlinearity is determined by the time constant, $\bar{\lambda}$. It is clear from equation (1) that for $(\bar{\lambda} \dot{\gamma}) \ll 1$ the viscosity becomes Newtonian. The power law exponent, n , determines the degree of nonlinearity. The value of $n=1$ corresponds to a Newtonian fluid, and as the exponent decreases the fluid exhibits increased shear thinning.

It has been stated (6), that the influence of temperature on viscosity can be represented as follows:

$$\bar{\eta}_0 = \eta_0 A_T; \bar{\lambda} = \lambda A_T \quad (2)$$

where the temperature shift factor, A_T , is defined as:

$$A_T = e^{-\xi(T/T_0)^{-1}} \quad (2a)$$

Note, the temperature shift factor as defined above is normalized so that at a given reference temperature, T_0 , the shift factor equals zero.

Viscosity versus shear rate data for typical high performance polymer PEEK at 399°C (7) is shown in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows the temperature shift factor versus temperature for PEEK (7). Equation (1) and equation (2a) were fit to the PEEK data thus determining the parameters as follows:

$$\eta_0 = 280 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{S}, \lambda = 0.038 \text{ S}, n = 0.781, \xi = 6.56$$

Equations (1) and (2a) are compared with the experimental data in Figures 1 and 2.

Employing this matrix constitutive relation and the development presented in reference (3) it is

possible to derive new expressions for effective viscosities of the medium as follows:

$$\eta_{11} = \frac{\eta_0 A_T (1-\mu) f}{2\mu} (L/D)^2 \left[1 + \frac{A_T^2 (1-\mu)^2 (L/D)^2}{4\mu^2} (\lambda \dot{\epsilon}_1)^2 \right]^{(n-1)/2} \quad (3a)$$

$$\eta_{22} = \frac{4\eta_0 A_T}{\mu} \left[1 + \frac{4A_T^2}{\mu^2} (\lambda \dot{\epsilon}_2)^2 \right]^{(n-1)/2} \quad (3b)$$

$$\eta_{12} = \frac{\eta_0 A_T (1+\mu)}{2\mu} \left[1 + \frac{A_T^2 (1+\mu)^2}{4\mu^2} (\lambda \dot{\gamma}_{12})^2 \right]^{(n-1)/2} \quad (3c)$$

$$\eta_{23} = \frac{\eta_0 A_T}{\mu} \left[1 + \frac{A_T^2}{\mu^2} (\lambda \dot{\gamma}_{23})^2 \right]^{(n-1)/2} \quad (3d)$$

where

$$\mu = 1 - \sqrt{f/F}; F = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi}{4} & \text{square array} \\ \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{3}} & \text{hexagonal array} \end{cases}$$

3. RESULTS

Given the material descriptors and matrix properties as a function of temperature and strain rate, equations (3a-d) can be utilized to predict the unique properties of the material. Figure 3 shows these predictions for the PEEK data discussed in section 2 in conjunction with a square array of 60 percent fiber volume content and a fiber aspect ratio of 10^4 . The figure illustrates the relative difference in the various effective viscosities. It is especially interesting that the maximum Newtonian strain rate is lower for the fiber filled polymer than for the neat polymer. This is especially evident in the longitudinal elongational viscosity which begins to exhibit the shear thinning phenomenon at an elongational strain rate approximately three magnitudes of order less than the fluid's maximum Newtonian strain rate.

Figure 4 shows the effect of temperature on the in-plane viscosity versus strain rate. Notice that an increase in temperature decreases the viscosity but increases the maximum range in rate over which Newtonian behavior is observed.

To gain a better understanding of the strain rate and temperature dependence a parametric study of the Carreau model parameters will be presented. Only the longitudinal elongational viscosity will be illustrated since the same general tendencies will hold for all the viscosities in equation (3). For large strain rate, it is clear that the quantity $(n-1)$ defines the slope of the viscosity versus strain rate curve on a log-log scale. This is illustrated in Figure 5 for values of the power law term in the range 0-1. Note that $n=1$ corresponds to the Newtonian case.

Using a log-log bi-linear approximation for the viscosity strain rate relation, an upper bound for the maximum Newtonian strain rate is

$$\dot{\epsilon}_N = \frac{2\mu}{A_T(1-\mu)(L/D)\lambda} \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) shows that as the time constant increases, $\dot{\epsilon}_N$ decreases. This effect of the time constant on $\dot{\epsilon}_N$ is illustrated in Figure 6. The influence of the fiber geometry on viscosity can also be observed by studying equation (4). Increases in L/D will result in a decrease in the maximum Newtonian Strain rate for the fiber assembly. The temperature dependency on the viscosity appears in the zero-shear viscosity and time constant. As the temperature shift factor increases, the zero-shear viscosity and the time constant decrease. This is illustrated in Figure 7 for various values of the temperature shift factor.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Relations for predicting the effective viscosities of an aligned discontinuous fiber filled fluid developed in (1-3) for Newtonian and power law fluids have been extended to include zero-shear viscosity and temperature dependence. This was accomplished by describing the matrix fluid viscosity with a Carreau model. Using experimentally determined viscosity data for PEEK, effective properties of a fiber assembly were predicted. It was shown that the introduction of fibers into the fluid can dramatically decrease the maximum Newtonian strain rate. This is critical when determining a maximum strain rate for which Newtonian behavior is expected. The effect of the Carreau model parameters on the elongational viscosity were demonstrated for a wide range of values.

In addition to long discontinuous fiber systems, the relationships presented in this paper, all but the longitudinal elongational viscosity prediction, are valid for continuous fiber systems. It should be kept in mind that these relations provide insight into the relative magnitudes of the predicted properties, the effect of material descriptors, and the degree of anisotropy of the medium.

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TABLE 1
Summary of Viscosity Predictions (3)

Term	Newtonian Fluid η : Shearing Viscosity	Power-Law Fluid $\tau = \tau_o + \eta \dot{\gamma}^m$
η_{11}/η	$\frac{f}{2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{f}}{1 - \sqrt{f}} \right] (L/D)^2$	$2^{-mf} \left[\frac{\sqrt{f}}{1 - \sqrt{f}} \right]^m (L/D)^{m+1} \dot{\epsilon}_1^{m-1}$
η_{12}/η	$\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{2 - \sqrt{f}}{1 - \sqrt{f}} \right]$	$2^{-m} \left[\frac{2 - \sqrt{f}}{1 - \sqrt{f}} \right]^m \dot{\gamma}_{12}^{m-1}$
η_{23}/η	$\left[1 - \sqrt{f} \right]^{-1}$	$\left[1 - \sqrt{f} \right]^{-m} \dot{\gamma}_{23}^{m-1}$
η_{22}/η	$4 \left[1 - \sqrt{f} \right]^{-1}$	$2^{(m+1)} \left[1 - \sqrt{f} \right]^{-m} \dot{\epsilon}_2^{m-1}$

NOMENCLATURE

<u>Symbol</u>	<u>Term</u>	<u>Units</u> [F,L,T,D]
A_T	Temperature shift factor	--
D	Fiber diameter	L
f	Fiber volume fraction	--
F	Maximum fiber volume fraction	--
L	Fiber length	L
n	Power law exponent	--
T	Temperature	D
T_0	Reference temperature	D
$\dot{\epsilon}_{11}$	Longitudinal elongational strain rate	1/T
$\dot{\epsilon}_{22}$	Transverse elongational strain rate	1/T
$\dot{\epsilon}_N$	Maximum Newtonian strain rate	1/T
$\dot{\gamma}$	Fluid shearing strain rate	1/T
$\dot{\gamma}_{12}$	In-plane shearing strain rate	1/T
$\dot{\gamma}_{23}$	Transverse shearing viscosity	1/T
η	Fluid viscosity	FT/L ²
η_0	Zero-shear viscosity	FT/L ²
η_{11}	Longitudinal elongational viscosity	FT/L ²
η_{22}	Transverse elongational viscosity	FT/L ²
η_{12}	In-plane shearing viscosity	FT/L ²
η_{23}	Transverse shearing viscosity	FT/L ²
λ	Time constant	T
ξ	Temperature shift factor constant	--

Figure 1: Experimental Data for Viscosity Versus Shear Rate for PEEK at 399°C.

Figure 2: Experimental Data for Temperature Shift Factor Versus Temperature for PEEK.

Figure 3: Effective Viscosities Versus Strain Rate for Fiber Reinforced PEEK at 399°C.

Figure 4: Effect of Temperature on In-plane Shearing Viscosity Versus Strain Rate for Fiber Reinforced PEEK.

Figure 5: Effect of Power Law Exponent on Longitudinal Elongational Viscosity Versus Strain Rate.

Figure 6: Effect of Time Constant on Longitudinal Elongational Viscosity Versus Strain Rate.

Figure 7: Effect of Temperature on Longitudinal Elongational Viscosity Versus Strain Rate.

